

SECURING ELECTRONIC MAIL SYSTEMS

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Abstract:

Securing electronic mail presents some unique challenges in that it is a staged delivery application, where the message originator and message recipient are not usually in real-time communications with each other. For applications such as electronic mail, network level encryption devices leave vulnerabilities at intermediate relay points such as mail servers or message transfer agents (MTAs).

Mail messages are typically decrypted, and stored RED (unprotected/unencrypted) at these repositories. Subsequently, they are re-encrypted and delivered to their destinations (see fig 1).

Security at the network layer can not provide application specific services associated with electronic mail such as signed receipts and digital signatures. These deficiencies can be remedied by providing end user to end user security where mail messages are black (protected/encrypted) at all intermediate points. This paper describes the approach and implementation taken in building such a mail security device. It shall address the key security services provided and possible implementations.

Approach:

The staged delivery (non-real time) nature of E-Mail levies the requirement that each security device must execute security relevant process/decisions (i.e., confidentiality, integrity, source authentication, access control) without a real-time exchange of information between cooperating parties. The large base of electronic mail users and their diverse connectivity requirements make the use of secret keys distributed from a trusted source impractical and undesirable. The mail protocol will use a staged key information exchange in which a user to receive secure mail posts his certificate and some public key information on a mail or directory server. The sender uses this posted information along with his own private information to process a pair-wise key encryption key, which is unique to the sender-receiver pair.

The protocol accommodates multi-addressing by using a single message key to encrypt the message and then using a pair-wise key, for each addressee, to encrypt the message key. The message header includes the sender's certificate. It also includes for each addressee, the public key information needed to process their pair-wise key, the encrypted key and the integrity check.

The electronic mail security device performs the following security functions.

- ENCRYPT MESSAGE
- OUTPUT CREDENTIALS
- HASH MESSAGE
- GENERATE SIGNATURE
- READ CREDENTIALS
- GENERATE KEYS
- ENCRYPT KEYS
- DECRYPT KEYS
- DECRYPT MESSAGE
- READ SIGNATURE

29.1.1

Credentials refer to a users certificate and public key information to include keying information needed for the generation of digital signatures.

System Operations:

The transmission of a secure electronic mail message involves a sequence of steps as shown in Table I. Each user has unique keying information which is bound to a non-forgable certificate. The certificate identifies the end user and their security privileges. Two users wishing to communicate exchange certificates and keying information. The exchange results in a key that is pair-wise unique between the two end users. Establishing a pair-wise key requires the principles to gather each other's public information. This information can be obtained from a mail/directory server much

in the same manner that phone numbers are taken from telephone books. The certificate is digitally signed by a certifying authority that all members trust. This eliminates the need for trust at the servers since certificates can neither be forged or altered. Certificates may also be cashed by end users to eliminate needless requests to the server.

The mail message format is shown in Figure 2.

Privacy of the message is achieved because only the correct recipient possesses the pair-wise key and can decrypt the message (steps 4,5,6,7,11,12,13). The source of the message is authenticated by the binding between the sender/receiver credentials and the pair-wise key (steps 1,2,3,10). The source of the message can

TABLE I - SECURE MAIL TRANSFER

SENDER	RECEIVER
	1. Transmit Recipients Credentials
2. Receive Credentials of Recipients	
3. Transmit Credentials of Sender	
4. Process Key (Key Encryption Key)	
5. Generate Key (Traffic Encryption Key)	
6. Encrypt Key (Encrypt TEK with KEK)	
7. Encrypt Message with TEK	
8. Hash Message	
9. Generate Signature	
	10. Receive Senders Credentials
	11. Process Key (KEK)
	12. Decrypt Key (TEK)
	13. Decrypt Message with TEK
	14. Read Signature
	15. Hash Message
	16. Generate Signature
17. Read Signature	

29.1.2

also be authenticated by the sender cryptographically signing the mail message. This can be useful if authentication without privacy is desired (steps 8,9,14,15). Authentication of end users identity is achieved through the exchange of non-forgeable certificates (steps

1,2,3,10). Integrity of the message is maintained through use of a digital signature appended to the message. Insertion, deletion or modification to the mail message results in an invalid signature at the receiver (steps 8,9,14,15). The mail transfer scenario

provides the capability of sending registered mail. The sender can not deny having sent mail since the sender is the only party to have his unique signature key (proof of origin) (steps 8,9). The receiver provides proof of delivery by resigning the hashword on the message with his unique signature key and sending the resigned hashword back to the sender (steps 15,16).

If link, network or transport layer security services are employed, they will act independently of the application layer security services discussed in this paper. The new architecture that arises from using the secure E-Mail device is shown in Figure

3. A network layer security device may be used to protect mail header information or to secure other types of data traffic not secured by the mail security device.

Summary: This paper described an approach at protecting mail messages along the entire path from originator to recipient. The messages are protected during storage and processing at all intermediate points. The security can be implemented independent of the network layer architecture or a network layer security device. The key distribution technique is suitable for client-server architectures such as E-mail where the number of users is large and connectivity is diverse.

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